

Figure 2. Functional annotation status of 673 genes studied by loss-of-function approaches in *M. truncatula*, based on the genome browser v. 5.1.9. (a) Six categories of loci based on their annotation status. The first element in each category’s code corresponds to a gene name (“Yes” - name assigned, “No” - name not assigned). More than one quarter (26%) of characterized genes are not named (Data S6 Column V). The second element in each category’s code corresponds to a reference (“Yes” - reference assigned, “No” - reference not assigned, “YN” for “Yes and No” - an irrelevant reference assigned). More than one quarter (27%) of characterized genes have no reference (Data S6 Column W). Among genes with a reference, 32% have only irrelevant references or references to transcriptomic studies/reviews instead of correct references to loss-of-function studies. (b) The distribution of 173 “missed” genes over their publication years (category “No/No”, no name and no reference in the genome browser v. 5.1.9). Only the year of the first loss-of-function publication is counted for each gene.